

A Mathematical Proof That Photons Are the Fundamental Particle of Gravity

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides a mathematical proof that the fundamental particle of gravity is the photon, and that gravity is caused by the electrostatic force of travelling photon pairs. There are three accepted formulas that describe the constant of gravity. The oldest of the three comes from Sir Isaac Newton who described the constant of gravity in a two-dimensional sense. The next accepted gravity constant formula from Planck in around 1899 which outlined the need for four constants to describe everything in the universe. This "everything" was later summed up by Einstein when he equated Energy to Mass. Einstein's now famous papers where he outlined relativity pointed out that Planck's mathematics were not exact but used a "mean." Einstein then came forth with his own constant of gravity and further the advent of Special Relativity; the special case in which Space-Time is flat. Here the writer first provides a mathematical proof equating Newton's, Planck's, and Einstein's gravity to each other and then uses the properties of photons to solve for 1 or identity. An unexpected result of this paper was finding a possible solution to special relativity.

INTRODUCTION

Through unit analysis, statistical mechanics, and the study of photonics the writer has developed a mathematical proof that gravity is a result of electrostatic forces caused by the interaction of photons and that photons are therefore the fundamental particles of gravity. The proof demonstrates that Newton's, Planck's, and Einstein's gravity constants are equivalent when and only when the properties of Photons are used. Classical Newtonian physics describe gravity using only two instances or dimensions; mass1 and mass2 in the denominator and the distance between them squared in the numerator.

$$G = \frac{r^2}{m_1 m_2}$$

*Where r is equal to distance between mass 1 and mass 2.

Planck stated that gravity needed 4 constants but contradicted his findings by only using a balance of 3 constants in his gravity constant formula:

$$G = \frac{l_p^3}{m_p t_p^2}$$

*Where l_p is the Planck length, m_p is the Planck mass, and t_p is the Planck time.

Here Planck took l_p to three instances in the numerator, which could be considered dimensions. t_p to two, and m_p to one for a total of three instances or dimensions to balance the equation. Planck used a mean formula to render the 4 constants to 3 thereby providing a "good-enough" formula but not an exact.

Einstein moved us closer to an answer by his gravitational constant which described gravity in all four dimensions of space and time:

$$k = \frac{8\pi G}{C^4}$$

Einstein's gravity constant holds true except for when large values of light interact with matter. This paper offers a solution to that problem by equating "G", which can represent either Gravity or the bend in spacetime caused by the gravity of the larger object, to $\frac{8\pi}{C^4}$. Asserting that Gravity is caused by light (photons) and that higher energy light will have a gravitational effect on light passing close by.

NATURE OF PHOTONS

Photons travel in tightly coupled di-pole pairs of energy quanta (Giertz, 2010) rotating around each other. The pairs are made up of a vertically polarized photon and a horizontally polarized photon. The photons are in constant rotation and the pair twists

around each other in a manor described by Riemannian manifolds with the geodesic taking place through within the manifold and not at the boundary. This intersection results in a tangent plane through the origin. (Riemannian Geometry, unknown) Deeper explanation of the Riemannian manifold is outside the scope of this paper. Photons do not have magnetic properties and it is the resultant of the configuration which produces electrostatic forces that propel photons in space and over time.

A known attribute of the gravity particle is that it has a spin of 2 and is massless as discovered by Steven Weinberg in 1964. (Liu) The photon is massless but has a spin of 1. Photons do not have a positive and negative spin which accounts for the photon not having electromagnetic forces, instead the photon is made up of two separate $\frac{1}{2}$ spins giving the photon its dipole nature. It is due to the spin 1 that a single photon is not able to produce gravity. The photonic pairing made of a vertical and horizontal polarized photon does have a combined spin of 2 satisfying Weinberg's assertion.

ANALYSIS AND PROOF

The writer begins by analyzing Einstein's constant of gravity as it is the most accurate and complete. Starting with the numerator.

π is used to describe rotation in space with 2π being a full rotation over all four quadrants or dimensions. Einstein's Zurich notebook (which is now available online with special thanks to John D. Norton and University of Pittsburgh) shows Einstein labeled the four dimensions as x, y, z, and ICT. The manifold representing the whole, split into four parts or quanta (V_u, V_d, H_u, H_d)¹, over four dimensions (2π), gives us the first unit in Einstein's gravitational constant:

$$4 * 2\pi = 8\pi$$

"C" in the denominator describes the speed of light and by raising "C" to the 4th power or dimension we are stating the distance travelled by each of the energy quanta with respect to time. The denominator represents the Scalar quantity.

8π in the numerator in the formula for electrostatic forces is represented by KE, kinetic energy in space. C^4 can be represented by PE; Potential energy or energy over distance where distance equals

rate*time. Rewriting Einstein's gravity constant with the substitutive values we get:

$$k = \frac{KE}{PE} * \frac{G}{1}$$

Setting k equal to 1 and solving for G we arrive at:

$$\frac{PE}{KE} = G$$

PE and KE must maintain a ratio of 1:1 to satisfy the laws of conservation.

Using the same process as above to investigate Planck's gravity constant:

$$G = \frac{l_p^3}{m_p t_p^2}$$

Where Planck describes Gravity using l_p or plank's length to the 3rd power/dimension. l_p in the numerator is the potential energy (PE); energy over distance with respect to time. And held in ratio with Planck mass * Planck time squared in the denominator. The denominator is the kinetic energy (KE) and is in three dimensions; two dimensions of time for one of mass. The ratio is 1:1 resulting in $G = 1$. (Ball, 2007)

Lastly when performing the same analysis on Newtons 2-D gravitational constant:

$$G = \frac{r^2}{m1 * m2}$$

Where r is equal to the distance between mass1 and mass2. The numerator again represents the potential energy and is held in ratio to the mass of object 1 * the mass of object 2. All three formulas result in $\frac{PE}{KE}$ therefore the following is true:

$$\frac{C^4}{8\pi} = \frac{l_p^3}{m_p t_p^2} = \frac{r^2}{m1 m2}$$

$$\frac{PE}{KE} \equiv G_p \equiv G$$

¹ The biggest detriment to advancing Scientific and Mathematical knowledge is arguably the English language. Here the Writer chose to label the $\frac{1}{2}$ spin as "u" which could mean up and "d" which could be read as down. The point is the four quanta.

The next step is to apply the previously discussed properties of photons to solve the three equations of gravity. Solving for the two dimensional Newtonian numerator PE, at the point of intersection between the pairs, the distance $r = 0$. Photons have a mass of zero, $m_1 = 0$ and $m_2 = 0$, therefore the denominator is 0^2 . Photons as the fundamental particle of gravity satisfies the identity:

$$G = \frac{0^2}{0^2}$$

$$G = 1$$

Graphing the above does not result in an "undetermined" as traditional thinking suggest. Rather graphing the above results in what Einstein predicted for special relativity. In the below fig 1 green represents the gravitational field on the z axis and the shaded grey region represents the photon pairs or light. The light can be seen traveling in opposing directions and at a 45 degree angle as predicted in special relativity. (Dilts, 2017) The angle shows the event in flat spacetime.

Fig 1

Perhaps more exciting is fig 2 which shows the event from the position of the observer in three dimensions. If the assertions in this paper are correct then this is what a gravity field would look like at the moment it is produced.

Fig 2

The above figure is the result of graphing the solution using x, y, z where x and y are equal to 0:

$$z = \frac{x^2}{y^2}$$

THE "SPECIAL" CASE OF $\frac{0}{0} = 1$

The general thinking of $0/0$ being undetermined has been a subject of great debate in the community and in the process of getting this paper peer reviewed. As such the Writer felt it necessary to address $0/0$ or the point of independence in better detail. Einstein called the condition where all points begin at the origin independence, stating that it is the point in which the system acts independently of any other system. A paper titled, "Zero Divided by Zero Equals One," describes the Law of Independence in length. (Barukčić, 2018).

Historically the Babylonians and Sumerians in the estimated time period of 5000-3000BC had created a system of numbers and mathematics using base 60. From this they were able to accurately chart the planet and stars, create calendars, and with surprising accuracy make predictions with Astrology. Their mathematics were very sophisticated and included the earliest recorded examples of multiplication and division. Division was accomplished by multiplying using reciprocals. The Babylonian formula for division is:

$$\frac{a}{b} = a \cdot \frac{1}{b}$$

If $a = 0$ and $b = 0$ then the result will be:

$$\frac{0}{0} = 0 \cdot \frac{1}{0}$$

Simplifying by cross-cancellation we get:

$$\frac{0}{0} = 1$$

Outside of multiplying by reciprocals the writer was able to find two cases of $0/0 = 1$ that relate to photons creating gravity. The first case explains the conditions in which the intersection of the two photons will result in a tangent plane through the origin.

Case 1:

$$\tan(x) = \sin(x)/\cos(x)$$

$$\tan(x) = 1 \text{ when } \sin(x) = 0 \text{ and } \cos(x) = 0$$

$$\sin(x) = 0 \text{ when } x \text{ is } (0, \pi, 2\pi)$$

$$\cos(x) = 0 \text{ when } x \text{ is } (\pm \frac{\pi}{2}, \pm \frac{3\pi}{2}, \pm \frac{5\pi}{2})$$

$$1 = \frac{0}{0}$$

To satisfy this condition the two systems (photons) would have to be out of phase which could be caused by a difference in the size of the systems or if one system's rotation was slowed. In special relativity, Einstein explained that the speed of the gravity particle, which is distance over rate, would have to be different than that of the matter being attracted.(Einstein) It is exactly the slowing of one of the pairs that causes gravity and that effect will continue to effect passing light until all particles in that clumping are moving at the same speed.

The below figure 3 is the graph:

Case 2:

$$x^2 = \frac{0}{0}$$

Where the system crosses the X axis at 1 and -1 and crosses Y axis at 0 and $\frac{1}{0}$. The resulting form is a manifold which describes how the two photons rotate around each other and gives an idea of how a single photon with two poles may travel. Figure 4 is not exact but gives a good visual as to how the vertical and horizontal photon pair is arranged and rotates around each other.

Manifold - Wikipedia
en.wikipedia.org

TANGIBLE PROOFS:

The claims made in this paper are supported by current technologies and physical phenomenon. The focus of this paper is the mathematical proof of photons as gravity and the writer will only skim the surface of the following applications.

Optical Tweezers exploit photon production of a gravity like field to attract or repel particles. (Lee, 2009) The tweezers do this by exploiting what is called Optical force. Optical force is made up of the gradient force F_g and the scattering and absorption force (kinetic force) F_k . By Stokes' Theorem $\nabla \times F_g = 0$ and by Optical Earnshaw Theorem $\nabla \times F_k = 0$ (Du et.al, 2017) By maintaining the ratio of F_g and F_k we are able to produce a gravity field whose strength is equivalent to the Energy levels of the laser used. The writer challenges researchers to verify this assertion. If photons cause gravity and mass must be equal to the energy produced, it is obvious that Photons have to be the fundamental particle of Mass as well. This fact is supported by how objects of resonant frequency interact with the optical tweezers. "When objects are resonant with the incident light, the optical force may be greatly enhanced...[the] single structure simultaneously supports both optical and mechanical resonances..."(Gao et.al, 2017) Optical forces (F_g , F_k) and mechanical forces (PE, KE) are equivalent as predicted in this paper.

The writer provides the following as a thought experiment and intends to go into the proof in a follow-on paper. Gravitational Lensing is the bending of light in the presence of an object of super mass. If the assertions in this paper are correct than photons as the particle of gravity explains gravitational lensing predicted by Einstein's theory of general relativity and proven in 1979 by astronomers at Kitt Peak National Observatory. (Daley, 2018) The photons of light would create gravity and light of lower energy would be trapped in the gravitational pull of high mass object until a sort of equilibrium in the mass was reached. Energies of light would be pulled towards the massive object due to gravity and would either be absorbed, break free do to its own gravitational properties such as rotation, or subject to refraction. Refraction is the slowing of light as it enters a medium or mass. That is to say light through the atmosphere of a planet would travel slower than light in a vacuum. The slowing of the light in space-time is part of relativity and the theorem of reality as a hologram.

CONCLUSION:

This paper has presented a mathematical proof that photons are the fundamental particle of Gravity and that their electrostatic forces cause objects to attract. Here the writer proved that:

$$\frac{C^4}{8\pi} = \frac{l_p^3}{m_p t_p^2} = \frac{r^2}{m_1 m_2}$$

$$\frac{PE}{KE} \equiv G_p \equiv G$$

The paper showed that photons travel in pairs and that coupling results in a massless particle that has a spin of 2. That the condition of the two-photon intersecting at the origin, out of phase so that the resulting tangent plane has the value of 1 is the event in which gravity waves are released. The findings in this paper begin to satisfy the conditions set forth in special relativity and general relativity and further investigation is necessary.

The paper hinted to photons then being the fundamental particle of all matter and the conditions in which matter is made as described in the Red Postulate. The findings as they relate to matter is reserved for a forthcoming paper by the Writer.

Since I am not in a position to do experimental work myself, I would be glad if a physicist would show an interest in the method described.

Einstein Annus Mirabilis Papers 1906

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